

Balancing Act: A Neutrosophic Approach to Human Rights and Values in Varied Societal Contexts

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Abstract. This article explores the challenges that arise when human rights come into conflict with cultural, political, and ethical values in diverse societies. Eight areas of discord related to human rights are identified, and four criteria are proposed to assess how human rights relate to these values. These criteria include universality and cultural relativism, contextualization, ethical pluralism, and equity and social justice. The evaluation is based on neutrosophic selection criteria, employing the COPRAS multicriteria method. This analytical and decision-making approach is applied to eight specific cases of conflicts between human rights and values, such as women's rights, freedom of expression, and others. The results obtained provide a solid foundation for understanding how human rights relate to cultural, political, and ethical values in diverse societies. The article highlights the importance of finding a balance between protecting fundamental rights and respecting cultural and ethical diversity in resolving these conflicts. The promotion and protection of human rights remain a fundamental goal of the international community, regardless of cultural, political, or ethical differences.

Keywords: COPRAS, neutrosophic selection criteria, human rights, values, conflict.

1. Introduction

Human rights are universal principles that protect the dignity and freedom of all human beings, regardless of race, religion, sex, nationality or any other status. Cultural, political, and ethical values are the beliefs and principles that guide the behavior of people and societies [1].

In some cases, human rights may conflict with cultural, political, and ethical values. This can occur for several reasons, such as:

- Differences in conceptions of human dignity: In some cultures, human dignity is grounded in adherence to traditional social norms, whereas in others, it is based on individual autonomy and freedom of choice.
- Differences in political priorities: Governments may prioritize economic development or national security over human rights.
- Differences in religious or moral beliefs: Certain religions or moral systems may deem specific behaviors acceptable, while human rights prohibit them.

Some examples of cases in which human rights have come into conflict with cultural, political, and ethical values are [2]:

Figure 1: Cases. Source: Own elaboration based on [2].

The resolution of conflicts between human rights and cultural, political, and ethical values is a complex challenge. There is no single solution for all cases. However, it is important to consider the following factors (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Factors to consider when resolving conflicts between human rights and values. Source: own elaboration.

The promotion and protection of human rights is a fundamental objective of the international community. Conflicts between human rights and cultural, political, and ethical values put this objective to the test [3]. However, it is important to remember that human rights are universal and must be protected regardless of cultural, political, or ethical differences [4].

Some examples of conflicts between human rights and cultural, political, and ethical values due to differences in perceptions and norms in different societies and contexts are:

1. **Women's Rights vs. Cultural Practices:** In some societies, cultural practices such as female genital mutilation or forced marriages conflict with women's rights to equality, physical integrity, and autonomy. The struggle to ensure women's rights often clashes with deeply rooted cultural norms.
2. **Freedom of Expression vs. Moral Protection:** In some countries, laws of defamation, blasphemy, or insult to the State can limit freedom of expression. This poses a conflict between the right to freedom of expression and the perceived need to protect morality or political stability.
3. **Right to Privacy vs. National Security:** National security concerns often clash with individuals' right to privacy. Mass surveillance measures, such as online data collection, raise questions about balancing security with respect for individual privacy.
4. **Right to Non-discrimination vs. Religious Practices:** In some cases, religious beliefs may conflict with the principle of non-discrimination. For example, the refusal of some religious institutions to marry or provide services to same-sex couples may clash with the equality and non-discrimination rights of these couples.
5. **Right to Life vs. Death Penalty:** The death penalty is a controversial issue in many countries. Some argue that the death penalty is necessary for justice and security, while others consider it inhumane and a violation of the right to life.
6. **Rights of Refugees vs. State Sovereignty:** When refugees flee conflicts or persecution in their home countries, they often seek refuge in other countries. This may conflict with state sovereignty, as governments may disagree on whether or not to admit refugees.
7. **Right to Freedom of Religion vs. Secular State:** In societies with a strict separation between church and state, conflicts arise when religious practices clash with laws or public policies. This may involve issues such as wearing the Islamic veil in public schools or the objection of some religious institutions to provide specific health services, such as contraception.
8. **Intellectual Property Rights vs. Access to Medicines and Technology:** Protecting intellectual property rights can hinder access to affordable medicines and medical technology in developing countries. This raises an ethical dilemma between protecting investment and ensuring access to basic needs.

In these cases, it is important to find a balance between respect for universal human rights and recognition of cultural, political, and ethical differences [5-15]. The challenges lie in how to reconcile these conflicts. In many cases, international courts, governments, and human rights organizations play an important role in resolving these dilemmas [6-13-16-17].

The objective of this research is to evaluate how human rights are related to cultural, political, and ethical values and their influence on societies.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 COPRAS method

The multicriteria decision-making technique proposed can be expressed in a general manner as described next. A decision-making problem is evaluated, consisting of m alternatives that must be assessed considering n criteria, and x_{ij} can be expressed as the value of the i -th alternative according to the j -th criterion [7], [8]. The main concept of the COPRAS technique consists of the steps described below:

Step1. Select the appropriate set of criteria that describes the chosen alternatives.

Step2. Prepare decision-making matrix X :

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{22} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Step 3. Determine the weights of the criteria w_j .

Step 4. Normalize the decision-making matrix \bar{X} . The values of the normalized matrix are determined as:

$$\bar{x}_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}}; i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

Step 5. Compute the weighted normalized decision-making matrix D , which components are calculated as

$$d_{ij} = \bar{x}_{ij} \cdot w_j; i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

Step 6. Calculate the sum of the criterion values with respect to optimization direction for each alternative

$$P_{+i} = \sum_{j=1}^{L_{max}} d_{+ij}; P_{-i} = \sum_{j=1}^{L_{min}} d_{-ij} \quad (4)$$

where d_{+ij} values correspond to the criteria to be maximized and values d_{-ij} correspond to the criteria to be minimized.

Step 7. Determine the minimal component of the P_{-i} :

$$P_{-min} = \min_i P_{-i}; i = 1, 2, \dots, L_{min} \quad (5)$$

Step 8. Determine the score value of each alternative Q_i :

$$Q_i = P_{+i} + \frac{P_{-min} \sum_{j=1}^{L_{min}} P_{-j}}{P_{-i} \sum_{j=1}^{L_{min}} \frac{P_{-min}}{P_{-j}}}; j = 1, \dots, L_{min} \quad (6)$$

Step 9. Determine optimality criterion K for the alternatives:

$$K = \max_i Q_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (7)$$

Step 10. Determine the priority of the alternatives. The greater score value Q_i for the alternative corresponds to the higher priority (rank) of the alternative.

2.2 Neutrosophic Sets

Definition 1. Let X be a space of the objects and $x \in X$. A neutrosophic set A in X is defined by three functions: truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy- membership function $I_A(x)$ and falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. These functions are defined on real standard or real non-standard subsets of $]0^-, 1^+[$. That is $T_A(x): X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$, $I_A(x): X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$ and $F_A(x): X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$. There is not any restriction on the sum of $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$, so $0^- \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3^+$.

2.2.1 Single-valued Neutrosophic Set

A single-valued neutrosophic set (SVNS) has been defined as described in [9].

Definition 2. Let X be a universal space of the objects and $x \in X$. A single valued neutrosophic set (SVNS) $\tilde{N} \subset X$ can be expressed as:

$$\tilde{N} = \{ \langle x, T_{\tilde{N}}(x), I_{\tilde{N}}(x), F_{\tilde{N}}(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad (8)$$

where $T_{\tilde{N}}(x): X \rightarrow]0, 1]$, $I_{\tilde{N}}(x): X \rightarrow]0, 1]$ and $F_{\tilde{N}}(x): X \rightarrow]0, 1]$

with $0 \leq T_{\tilde{N}}(x) + I_{\tilde{N}}(x) + F_{\tilde{N}}(x) \leq 3$ or all $x \in X$. The values $T_{\tilde{N}}(x)$, $I_{\tilde{N}}(x)$, and $F_{\tilde{N}}(x)$ represent the degrees of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership, and falsity-membership of x with respect to \tilde{N} , respectively [10]. When the set X contains only a single element, \tilde{N} is referred to as a single-valued neutrosophic number [11]. To simplify matters, a single-valued neutrosophic number is denoted as $\tilde{N}_A = (t_A, i_A, f_A)$, where t_A , i_A , and f_A are all within the range $[0, 1]$, and their sum satisfies the condition $0 \leq t_A + i_A + f_A \leq 3$.

Definition 3. Let $\tilde{N}_1 = (t_1, i_1, f_1)$ and $\tilde{N}_2 = (t_2, i_2, f_2)$ be two SVN numbers, then the sum of \tilde{N}_1 and \tilde{N}_2 is defined as follows:

$$\tilde{N}_1 + \tilde{N}_2 = (t_1 + t_2 - t_1 t_2, i_1 i_2, f_1 f_2) \quad (9)$$

Definition 4. Let $\tilde{N}_1 = (t_1, i_1, f_1)$ and $\tilde{N}_2 = (t_2, i_2, f_2)$ be two SVN numbers, then multiplication between \tilde{N}_1

and \tilde{N}_2 is defined as follows:

$$\tilde{N}_1 * \tilde{N}_2 = (t_1 t_2, i_1 + i_2 - i_1 i_2, f_1 + f_2 - f_1 f_2) \tag{10}$$

Definition 5. Let $\tilde{N} = (t, i, f)$ be an SVN number and $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ an arbitrary positive real number, then:

$$\lambda \tilde{N} = (1 - (1 - t)^\lambda, i^\lambda, f^\lambda), \lambda > 0 \tag{11}$$

Definition 6. If $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$, and $B = \{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n\}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) are two single-valued neutrosophic sets, then the separation measure between A and B applying the normalized Euclidian distance can be expressed as follows:

$$q_n(A, B) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left((t_A(x_i) - t_B(x_i))^2 + (i_A(x_i) - i_B(x_i))^2 + (f_A(x_i) - f_B(x_i))^2 \right)} \tag{12}$$

$(i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$

Definition 7. Let $A = (a, b, c)$ be a single-valued neutrosophic number, a score function is mapped \tilde{N}_A into the single crisp output $S(\tilde{N}_A)$ as follows

$$S(\tilde{N}_A) = \frac{3+t_A-2i_A-f_A}{4} \tag{13}$$

where $S(\tilde{N}_A) \in [0,1]$. This score function allows to have the results in the same interval since single-valued neutrosophic numbers are used.

The notion of a linguistic variable proves to be highly valuable in addressing decision-making challenges of an intricate nature. A linguistic variable's magnitude is denoted as a component within its set of terms. These linguistic magnitudes can be effectively represented using single-valued neutrosophic numbers.

Within this approach, we involve k decision-makers, m alternatives, and n criteria. The k decision-makers assess the significance of m alternatives across n criteria and establish rankings for the performance of the n criteria based on linguistic statements that have been transformed into single-valued neutrosophic numbers. The weights of importance, derived from single-valued neutrosophic values of linguistic expressions, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Linguistic variable and SVNSs. Source: [12].

Linguistic terms	SVNSs
Extremely good (EG) / 10 points	(1.00, 0.00, 0.00)
Very very good (VVG) / 9 points	(0.90, 0.10, 0.10)
Very good (VG) / 8 points	(0.80, 0.15, 0.20)
Good (G) / 7 points	(0.70, 0.25, 0.30)
Moderately good (MG) / 6 points	(0.60, 0.35, 0.40)
Medium (M) / 5 points	(0.50, 0.50, 0.50)
Moderately bad (MB) / 4 points	(0.40, 0.65, 0.60)
Bad (B) / 3 points	(0.30, 0.75, 0.70)
Very bad (VB) / 2 points	(0.20, 0.85, 0.80)
Very very bad (VVB) / 1 point	(0.10, 0.90, 0.90)
Extremely bad (EB) / 0 points	(0.00, 1.00, 1.00)

The performance of the group decision-making applying the COPRAS-SVNS approach can be described by the following steps.

- Step 1. Determine the importance of the experts. In the case when the decision is made by a group of experts (decision-makers), firstly the importance of the final decision of each expert is determined. If a vector $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k)$ is the vector describing the importance of each expert, where $\lambda_k \geq 0$ and $\sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k = 1$.
- Step 2. At this point, each decision-maker performs his evaluations concerning the ratings of the alternatives with respect to the attributes and the weights of the attributes. If the k^{th} expert's evaluation of the i^{th} alternative by the j^{th} criterion is denoted by $x_{ij}^k, i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. This evaluation is expressed in linguistic terms presented in Table 1. So, the decision matrix for any particular expert can be constructed

$$X^k = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11}^k & x_{12}^k & \dots & x_{1n}^k \\ x_{21}^k & x_{22}^k & \dots & x_{2n}^k \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ x_{m1}^k & x_{m2}^k & \dots & x_{mn}^k \end{bmatrix} \tag{14}$$

- Step 3. Calculate the weights of the criteria. The aggregated weights of the criteria are determined by $w_j = \lambda_1 w_j^{(1)} \cup \lambda_2 w_j^{(2)} \cup \dots \cup \lambda_k w_j^{(k)} = \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^K (1 - t_j^{(w_k)})^{\lambda_k}, \prod_{k=1}^K (i_j^{(w_k)})^{\lambda_k}, \prod_{k=1}^K (f_j^{(w_k)})^{\lambda_k}\right)$ (15)

- Step 4. Construction of the aggregated weighted single-valued decision matrix

$$\tilde{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{x}_{11} & \tilde{x}_{12} & \dots & \tilde{x}_{1n} \\ \tilde{x}_{22} & \tilde{x}_{22} & \dots & \tilde{x}_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ \tilde{x}_{m1} & \tilde{x}_{m2} & \dots & \tilde{x}_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where any particular element $\tilde{x}_{ij} = (\tilde{t}_{ij}, \tilde{i}_{ij}, \tilde{f}_{ij})$ represents the rating of the alternative A_i with respect to the j criterion and is determined as follows

$$\tilde{x}_{ij} = \lambda_1 x_{ij}^{(1)} \cup \lambda_2 x_{ij}^{(2)} \cup \dots \cup \lambda_k x_{ij}^{(k)} = \left(1 - \prod_{k=1}^K (1 - t_j^{(x_k)})^{\lambda_k}, \prod_{k=1}^K (i_j^{(x_k)})^{\lambda_k}, \prod_{k=1}^K (f_j^{(x_k)})^{\lambda_k}\right) \quad (17)$$

- Step 5. Determine the weighted decision matrix. Following Equation (3), the weighted decision matrix can be expressed as $D = [d_{ij}]$, $d = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where $d_{ij} = \tilde{x}_{ij} * w_j$. Applying Equation (10), a single element of the weighted decision matrix can be calculated

$$d_{ij} = t_{ij}^{\tilde{x}} t_j^w, i_{ij}^{\tilde{x}} + i_j^w - i_{ij}^{\tilde{x}} i_j^w, f_{ij}^{\tilde{x}} + f_j^w - f_{ij}^{\tilde{x}} f_j^w \quad (18)$$

- Step 6. Calculate the summation of the values for the benefit. Let $L_+ = \{1, 2, \dots, L_{max}\}$ be a set of the criteria to be maximized. Then the index of the benefit for each alternative can be determined

$$P_{+i} = \sum_{j=1}^{L_{max}} d_{+ij} \quad (19)$$

where the sum of the single value neutrosophic numbers is calculated by applying Equation (9).

- Step 7. Calculate the summation of the values for cost. Let be $L_- = \{1, 2, \dots, L_{min}\}$ a set of criteria to be minimized. Then the index of the cost of each alternative can be determined

$$P_{-i} = \sum_{j=1}^{L_{min}} d_{-ij} \quad (20)$$

- Step 8. Determine the minimal value of the P_{-i} .

- Step 9. Determine the score value of each alternative Q_i . In the beginning, the score values are calculated from the aggregated values for benefit and cost $S(P_{+i})$ and $S(P_{-i})$ applying Equation (13). The score values of the alternatives can be expressed as

$$Q_i = S(P_{+i}) + \frac{S(P_{-min}) \sum_{i=1}^{L_{min}} S(P_{-i})}{S(P_{-min}) \sum_{i=1}^{L_{min}} \frac{S(P_{-min})}{S(P_{-i})}} \quad (21)$$

- Step 10. Determine the optimality criterion K for the alternatives:

$$K = \max_i Q_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (22)$$

- Step 11. Determine the priority of the alternatives. The greater score value Q_i for the alternative corresponds to the highest priority (rank) of the alternative.

3 Results and Discussion

The exploration of the document base led to the identification of a series of controversies related to human rights that must be considered for the desired analysis. In total, eight areas of discord have been detected and proposed as options to be evaluated in the context of this study. To assess how human rights relate to cultural, political, and ethical values, four criteria are taken into account, which have been generated through a brainstorming process and then endorsed by expert consensus:

1. **Universality and cultural relativism:** It is necessary to consider whether human rights are perceived as universal, i.e., applicable in all cultures, or if there are cultural differences that can influence the interpretation and implementation of certain rights. Balancing the universality of rights with respect for cultural diversity is important.
2. **Contextualization:** It evaluates whether human rights can be adapted to the cultural, political, and ethical circumstances of a particular society without compromising their essence. Contextualization involves finding a balance between universal values and cultural specificities.
3. **Ethical pluralism:** It considers whether ethical pluralism is respected and protected, i.e., if the coexistence of different ethical value systems in a society is allowed without violating fundamental rights.
4. **Equity and social justice:** It verifies whether cultural and political policies and practices contribute to the promotion of equity and social justice, which in turn can influence the realization of economic and social rights.

These criteria help assess how human rights relate to the cultural, political, and ethical values of a society and how potential conflicts in this context can be addressed. The evaluation should seek a balance between the

protection of fundamental rights and respect for cultural and ethical diversity.

The evaluation involves the participation of 5 specialists in the relevant research field. The high relevance of all these experts is valued due to their extensive experience in the subject matter. The criteria are weighted based on the assessments of the specialists, taking into account the values presented in Table 1. As a result, Table 2 displays the set of weights obtained after implementing Equation (15).

Table 2: Vector of weights of the analyzed criteria. Source: own elaboration.

Criteria weights	SVNN
w_1	(0.87989;0.12011;0.11487)
w_2	(0.83428;0.16572;0.15849)
w_3	(0.82671;0.17329;0.15157)
w_4	(0.85573;0.14427;0.13195)

Specialists analyze the choice options considering how the criteria influence them, according to the values presented in Table 1. Subsequently, the acquired data are transformed into sets of neutral information for application in analysis, as shown in the following tables:

Table 3: Evaluation of decision alternatives with respect to Criterion 1: Universality and cultural relativism. Source: own elaboration.

Alternatives	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	Expert 5
Rights of women	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)
Freedom of expression	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)
Right to privacy	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)
Right to non-discrimination	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)
Right to life	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Rights of refugees	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)
Right to religious freedom	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Intellectual property rights	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)

Table 4: Evaluation of the decision alternatives with respect to Criterion 2: Contextualization. Source: own elaboration.

Alternatives	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	Expert 5
Rights of women	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)
Freedom of expression	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Right to privacy	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)
Right to non-discrimination	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)
Right to life	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Rights of refugees	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)
Right to religious freedom	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Intellectual property rights	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)

Table 5: Evaluation of decision alternatives with respect to Criterion 3: Ethical pluralism. Source: own elaboration.

Alternatives	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	Expert 5
Rights of women	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)
Freedom of expression	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)
Right to privacy	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Right to non-discrimination	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)
Right to life	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Rights of refugees	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)
Right to religious freedom	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Intellectual property rights	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)

Table 6: Evaluation of the decision alternatives with respect to Criterion 4: Equity and social justice. Source: own elaboration.

Alternatives	Expert 1	Expert 2	Expert 3	Expert 4	Expert 5
Rights of women	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)
Freedom of expression	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Right to privacy	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)
Right to non-discrimination	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)
Right to life	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Rights of refugees	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)
Right to religious freedom	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)
Intellectual property rights	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.75,0.25,0.2)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)

The analyses carried out by professionals serve as the foundation on which the operations mentioned in the process intended to create the decision matrix are executed. Once formula (17) is applied, the initial decision matrix is generated (Table 7), in which the results obtained after carrying out the indicated method are presented.

Table 7: Initial decision matrix. Source: own elaboration.

Alternatives/Criteria	Universality and cultural relativism	Contextualization	Ethical pluralism	Equity and social justice
Rights of women	(0.67,0.33,0.289)	(0.725,0.275,0.251)	(0.35,0.75,0.8)	(0.725,0.275,0.251)
Freedom of expression	(0.81,0.19,0.19)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	(0.383,0.692,0.728)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)
Right to privacy	(0.88,0.12,0.115)	(0.81,0.19,0.19)	(0.621,0.379,0.347)	(0.81,0.19,0.19)
Right to non-discrimination	(0.725,0.275,0.251)	(0.725,0.275,0.251)	(0.685,0.315,0.302)	(0.725,0.275,0.251)
Right to life	(0.685,0.315,0.302)	(0.618,0.393,0.398)	(0.685,0.315,0.302)	(0.445,0.588,0.603)
Rights of refugees	(0.621,0.379,0.347)	(0.601,0.411,0.381)	(0.541,0.472,0.457)	(0.491,0.555,0.552)
Right to religious freedom	(0.67,0.33,0.289)	(0.601,0.411,0.381)	(0.601,0.411,0.381)	(0.652,0.358,0.317)
Intellectual property rights	(0.621,0.379,0.347)	(0.565,0.435,0.416)	(0.445,0.588,0.603)	(0.541,0.472,0.457)

Starting from the initial decision matrix acquired, the implementation of the required modifications continues according to the approach of the method used to solve the problem and obtain the desired results. By using equation (19), the weighted decision matrix is generated, the results of which are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Weighted decision matrix. Source: own elaboration.

Alternatives	Risk of Recidivism	Social reintegration capacity	Family reintegration capacity	Repair of the prejudice caused
Rights of women	(0.59;0.41;0.371)	(0.605;0.395;0.37)	(0.289;0.793;0.83)	(0.62;0.38;0.35)
Freedom of expression	(0.713;0.287;0.283)	(0.417;0.583;0.579)	(0.317;0.745;0.769)	(0.428;0.572;0.566)
Right to privacy	(0.774;0.226;0.217)	(0.676;0.324;0.318)	(0.513;0.487;0.446)	(0.693;0.307;0.297)
Right to non-discrimination	(0.638;0.362;0.337)	(0.605;0.395;0.37)	(0.566;0.434;0.408)	(0.62;0.38;0.35)
Right to life	(0.603;0.397;0.382)	(0.516;0.494;0.493)	(0.566;0.434;0.408)	(0.381;0.647;0.655)
Rights of refugees	(0.546;0.454;0.422)	(0.501;0.509;0.479)	(0.447;0.563;0.539)	(0.42;0.619;0.611)
Right to religious freedom	(0.59;0.41;0.371)	(0.501;0.509;0.479)	(0.497;0.513;0.475)	(0.558;0.451;0.407)
Intellectual property rights	(0.546;0.454;0.422)	(0.471;0.529;0.509)	(0.368;0.659;0.663)	(0.463;0.548;0.529)

This examination makes it possible to identify the factors proposed by the method under consideration to choose between the available options. Table 9 shows the results achieved after carrying out the appropriate procedures.

Table 9: Pi, S(P) values, and Q score values for each alternative. Source: own elaboration.

Measures	Pi+	Pi-	S(P+)	S(P-)	Q
Rights of women	(0.893; 0.119; 0.107)	(0.59; 0.41; 0.371)	0.89	0.6000	1.54
Freedom of expression	(0.772; 0.248; 0.252)	(0.713; 0.287; 0.283)	0.76	0.7140	1.31
Right to privacy	(0.951; 0.049; 0.042)	(0.774; 0.226; 0.217)	0.95	0.7760	1.46
Right to non-discrimination	(0.935; 0.065; 0.053)	(0.638; 0.362; 0.337)	0.94	0.6440	1.55
Right to life	(0.87; 0.138; 0.132)	(0.603; 0.397; 0.382)	0.87	0.6070	1.51
Rights of refugees	(0.84; 0.178; 0.158)	(0.546; 0.454; 0.422)	0.83	0.5540	1.54
Right to religious freedom	(0.889; 0.118; 0.093)	(0.59; 0.41; 0.371)	0.89	0.6000	1.55
Intellectual property rights	(0.821; 0.191; 0.178)	(0.546; 0.454; 0.422)	0.82	0.5540	1.53

Table 9 shows the values of Pi, S(P), and the score Q for each alternative. According to these results, the human rights that experts have considered of greatest importance in the context of cultural, political, and ethical values are the right to non-discrimination and the right to religious freedom. These findings provide a solid foundation for the discussion and analysis of the interaction of human rights with cultural and ethical values in the society under study.

In terms of specific results, it is observed that experts have different perceptions and evaluations of the options. This underscores the complexity of issues related to human rights and their relationship with cultural, political, and ethical values. For example, in the case of women's rights, some experts valued the importance of contextualization and ethical pluralism, while others emphasized universality and cultural relativism. These differences reflect the diversity of opinions and approaches in interpreting human rights.

It is crucial to recognize that resolving conflicts between human rights and cultural, political, and ethical values is a complex challenge, and there is no one-size-fits-all solution. However, international courts, governments, and human rights organizations play a significant role in resolving these dilemmas. The promotion and protection of

human rights remain a fundamental goal of the international community, and it is essential to remember that these rights are universal and should be protected irrespective of cultural, political, or ethical differences.

This study contributes to understanding how human rights relate to cultural, political, and ethical values, and how these conflicts can be addressed. As societies evolve and change, ongoing reflection on these issues is crucial to ensure that human rights continue to be a cornerstone of justice and equity worldwide.

Conclusions

This scientific article has explored the relationship between human rights and cultural, political, and ethical values in different contexts. Eight areas of controversy were identified and evaluated through four criteria: universality and cultural relativism, contextualization, ethical pluralism, and equity and social justice. These criteria allowed for the assessment of how human rights relate to cultural, political, and ethical values and how potential conflicts in this context can be addressed.

The results demonstrate that the perception of the universality of human rights varies depending on the case and the influence of cultural, political, and ethical values. The contextualization of human rights is considered essential to balance universal values with cultural specificities. Ethical pluralism and the protection of different ethical value systems are important for maintaining cultural diversity. Additionally, the importance of policies and practices contributing to equity and social justice for the realization of economic and social rights is highlighted.

Resolving conflicts between human rights and cultural, political, and ethical values is a complex challenge that requires delicate balance. The involvement of experts and the weighting of criteria are useful tools for addressing these challenges and finding solutions that protect fundamental rights while respecting cultural and ethical diversity. Ultimately, the promotion and protection of human rights must remain a fundamental goal of the international community, regardless of cultural, political, or ethical differences.

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